

The Problem of Digital Trust and Readiness to Use Digital Technologies among Adolescents and Parents in Russia

Dmitrii I. Dubrov¹

¹ HSE University, Moscow, 101000, Russia

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to study digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies among adolescents and parents. To achieve this goal, an empirical validation of the construct “Digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies,” a methodology for its measurement, and a descriptive analysis of the data obtained among adolescents and parents were conducted. The descriptive data analysis showed that, for almost all indicators of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies, both similarities and significant differences between parents and adolescents were observed. Adolescents demonstrate higher digital trust and greater readiness to use digital technologies in their daily lives compared to parents. The discussion presents possible explanations for the identified similarities and differences, as well as ways to overcome the problem of low digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies in Russia.

Keywords

digital trust, digital technologies, readiness to use digital technologies, adolescents, parents

JEL codes: E71, I30, J13, L86

Introduction

We are currently witnessing rapid digitalization, which has accelerated as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and is now evident in almost all spheres of daily life. This process has led to the emergence of new digital technologies that facilitate information search and exchange, improve the security of financial transactions, and help reduce both financial and time costs (Koch and Koch 2019). In line with the development plans of the Russian

Federation until 2030, the active digitalization of strategic sectors of the national economy as well as of households has been identified as a priority. Achieving these long-term goals requires the active involvement of the population. It is therefore important to assess whether citizens are ready to take on this task.

However, statistics indicate significant heterogeneity in the adoption of new digital technologies in Russia. Studies show that young people under the age of 20 remain active users of such technologies (Veselov 2020; Zhuravlev and Nestik 2018). By contrast, one of the possible and relatively underexplored reasons for the limited use of digital technologies by the older generation is their distrust of these tools and their reluctance to integrate them into everyday life (Soldatova et al. 2021). For this reason, examining digital trust and readiness to adopt digital technologies is particularly important, as these factors represent key conditions for the successful introduction of digital innovations into the daily lives of Russian citizens.

At the same time, it remains unclear whether there are intergenerational differences in Russia with regard to digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies. If such differences exist, which other socio-demographic characteristics are associated with them?

In addition, it should be noted that the very concepts of “readiness to use digital technologies” and “digital trust” remain empirically underdeveloped, with no valid measurement tools currently available in Russian. Therefore, before addressing the research problem outlined above, it is necessary to operationalize these constructs.

In Russian-language dictionaries, readiness is typically defined as a voluntary expression of consent to perform certain actions, as well as a manifestation of willingness and aspiration for cooperation and assistance (Fedorova and Scheglova 2010). This notion is inseparable from people’s intentions, willingness, and consent. Importantly, an individual’s perception of new tools, products, or technologies is closely linked to their confidence in the safety of their use. This indicates an intrinsic connection with digital trust, generally understood as people’s confidence in the security of digital technologies.

Applied to the context of digital technologies, this means that the user not only agrees to adopt and has the necessary knowledge to employ them, but also feels confident and safe when interacting with digital tools. On this basis, we concluded that it is necessary to assess the level of digital readiness of the population using two key indicators: (1) the level of digital literacy and (2) the degree of trust in digital technologies. These criteria make it possible to evaluate comprehensively an individual’s readiness for the functional use of modern digital solutions. However, it first remains essential to identify the specific parameters that constitute digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies. This served as the foundation for our attempt to empirically validate the structure of this construct and to develop a reliable tool for its measurement across different age groups.

Referring to international experience in studying this issue – for example, the Digital Development Index (DEI) – it is important to emphasize that digital trust is a key factor in assessing countries’ readiness to integrate innovations and represents a fundamental driver of progress in the global digital economy. Digital trust rests on three main pillars: the protection of user privacy (including support for anonymity), Internet security, and the accountability of service providers (Digital Society Index 2019). Other studies define digital trust in terms of users’ confidence in data protection and privacy on digital platforms, the ability of platforms to provide safe spaces for expression and exchange of opinions, and users’ attitudes toward advertising (US Digital Trust Study).

Soomro et al. (2020) argue that, alongside the technological readiness of digital systems to provide a comfortable user experience, equal importance should be given to the readiness of users themselves – their skills, attitudes, and abilities – which serve as the main driving forces in achieving digital readiness and alignment with evolving technologies. Accordingly, an effective digital society depends on the development of the population's digital competencies, which are becoming increasingly vital in the context of rapid technological diffusion. These competencies are not limited to the technical ability to use digital tools, but also encompass the knowledge and ethical awareness necessary for intelligent and responsible interaction in the digital environment.

Using the framework proposed by Calvani et al. (2009), which outlines the structure of digital competencies, we can observe a comprehensive approach to defining digital literacy. The authors identify three key dimensions: technological, cognitive, and ethical. The technological dimension reflects the ability to engage with digital technologies flexibly and to create and disseminate new knowledge. The cognitive dimension involves the capacity to analyze and critically evaluate large volumes of digital information, assessing its meaning and reliability. This, in turn, enables individuals to draw sound conclusions and make informed decisions. The ethical dimension emphasizes the responsible use of technologies in interactions with others, which forms the basis for building trust and respect in the digital environment (Calvani et al. 2009). Taken together, these three dimensions determine not only the capacity of individuals to adapt to ongoing digital transformations, but also their potential to contribute to the development of a safe and sustainable digital society.

An equally important aspect of readiness to use digital technologies is an individual's belief in their own ability to master and apply them. This principle of self-efficacy suggests that confidence in one's abilities, combined with a sense of control over external factors influencing actions, can activate and optimize the effective use of digital tools (Abdulrazaq and Razlani 2020; Ajzen 1985; Bandura 1977).

Thus, the literature review allows us to identify the following key components of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies: reliability, security, confidentiality, and digital literacy. On the basis of these components, we developed a methodology for measuring digital trust and readiness and validated the structure of this construct on samples of adolescents and parents (see the section Research Methodology).

The next step is to consider which socio-demographic parameters may account for differences in levels of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies. Previous research indicates that individuals with higher socio-economic status (income and education level) possess greater material and cognitive resources for mastering digital technologies, particularly with regard to improving digital literacy. Moreover, people in higher socio-economic groups generally demonstrate higher levels of trust compared to those with lower socio-economic status (Alesina and La Ferrara 2002; Putnam 2000). This can be explained by the fact that individuals with higher socio-economic status are more likely to have positive interaction experiences within their social environment (Gallo et al. 2006). Therefore, differences in digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies can reasonably be expected across socio-economic groups.

In addition, differences may also arise depending on the degree of religiosity. However, these differences are shaped by the broader socio-cultural context, including the specifics of religious affiliation and the practices adopted within particular religious communities (Orlandi et al. 2022). For instance, in Russia, certain Orthodox groups exhibit a pronounced

mistrust toward new technologies that have already become commonplace in everyday life (e.g., barcodes, QR codes).

Recent studies further suggest that digital readiness and trust are influenced by the socioeconomic conditions of one's region of residence (Strazzullo 2024). In economically developed regions, individuals generally have greater opportunities to acquire and use digital technologies than residents of disadvantaged regions, where access to the Internet and modern digital devices may be severely limited. Moreover, economically developed regions typically offer broader educational opportunities and more high-paying jobs, which foster a larger share of individuals with high socioeconomic status – a factor that, as noted above, is positively associated with digital trust. Given the uneven socioeconomic development across Russian regions, regional disparities in digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies are therefore to be expected.

Thus, the main study aims to address the following research question: Are there differences in the levels of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies across key socio-demographic characteristics – namely, age, income, education, degree of religiosity, and region of residence – among parents and adolescents?

Sample

The survey was conducted among parents and adolescents. A total of 594 participants took part in the main study, of whom 297 were parents (108 males and 189 females) and 297 were adolescents (121 males and 176 females). The average age of parents was 46 years (SD = 1.31), and the average age of adolescents was 16 years (SD = 0.34). All participants were Russian. Table 1 presents the remaining socio-demographic characteristics.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the study sample

Socio-demographic characteristics	Parents, n (%)	Adolescents, n (%)
Family income		
[1] We live on this income without experiencing financial difficulties	57 (19.2%)	
[2] This income is basically enough for us	118 (39.7%)	
[3] It is quite difficult to live on such an income.	53 (17.9%)	
[4] It is very difficult to live on such an income.	69 (23.2%)	
Place of residence		
Yaroslavl oblast	144	144
Moscow	153	153
Level of religiosity (1-10)	7	5
Level of education		
Higher education	142 (47.7%)	
Secondary vocational	107 (36.2%)	
General average	48 (16.1%)	

Procedure

Empirical data for this study were collected at secondary vocational education institutions in Yaroslavl Oblast and the city of Moscow. The survey was conducted during extracurricular activities. Adolescents completed the questionnaire after school, and one copy of the questionnaire was provided to one of each adolescent's parents to complete. The survey was anonymous, although the questionnaires were coded for data management purposes. Participants did not receive any material compensation for taking part in the survey.

Research methodology

The procedure for empirical validation of the measurement method was carried out in three stages. In the first stage, 357 participants were surveyed, including 143 parents (62 males and 81 females) and 214 adolescents (106 males and 108 females). The average age of parents was 43 years ($SD = 1.27$), and the average age of adolescents was 16 years ($SD = 0.39$). At this stage, the factor structure of the measured construct of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies was tested on the adolescent and parent samples using confirmatory factor analysis. Items with low factor loadings were removed during the analysis [Appendix, Figures A1-A2]. Additionally, the internal consistency of the scales was assessed after modification using Cronbach's alpha coefficient analysis [Appendix, Tables A1-A2].

The second stage focused on assessing the convergent validity of the developed methodology. Convergent validity refers to the extent to which the measured construct is able to predict related variables (Campbell and Fiske 1959). The objective of this stage was to determine whether the constructs measured using our method would explain variance in a dependent variable. Based on the literature, we identified that one potential effect of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies is involvement in the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) (Veselov 2020; Zhuravlev and Nestik 2018; Vidasova and Kabanov 2020). This variable was measured using the appropriate methodology (Tatarko et al. 2020). Path analysis of the obtained data indicated that the validated construct significantly and positively predicts involvement in ICT use [Appendix, Figures A3-A4].

The third and final stage focused on assessing concurrent validity, which reflects the extent to which the measured construct is related to data obtained using methods that assess constructs similar in content (Campbell and Fiske 1959). To evaluate this type of validity, we employed a questionnaire on attitudes toward technology, administered separately to adolescents and parents (Soldatova et al. 2021). Previous studies have indicated that the constructs under investigation are expected to be generally related (Zhuravlev and Nestik 2018; Hunady et al. 2020). Spearman correlation analysis demonstrated a significant relationship between the variables in both samples [Appendix, Tables A3].

A descriptive analysis of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies was conducted using the methodology developed and validated in this study (see the Sample and Procedure sections above). The measurement methodology was applied in two versions, tailored to parents and adolescents, respectively. The following section provides a description of the scales and presents data on internal consistency (parents/adolescents).

Reliability. This scale measures the degree to which an individual perceives the trustworthiness of the digital technologies they use. Example items include: "I feel that most of the

digital technologies offered to us are reliable” and “I feel that the mobile applications I use are reliable” ($\alpha = 0.77/0.76$ for parents/adolescents).

Safety. This scale assesses the extent to which an individual perceives the safety of the digital technologies they use. Example items include: “I feel that most digital technologies offered to us are safe” and “I feel that the mobile applications I use will not harm my phone” ($\alpha = 0.83/0.85$ for parents/adolescents).

Confidentiality. This scale evaluates the perceived privacy of an individual’s digital technologies. Example items include: “I feel that most digital technologies offered to us store our personal data securely” and “I believe that the mobile applications I use will not share my information with strangers” ($\alpha = 0.85/0.86$ for parents/adolescents).

Digital literacy. This scale measures an individual’s perceived level of digital literacy. Example items include: “I feel that I can use most of the digital technologies offered to us on my own without any problems” and “I feel that I can easily master a new mobile application” ($\alpha = 0.72/0.74$ for parents/adolescents).

Digital Trust and Readiness. The overall level of digital trust and readiness was calculated as a composite coefficient across all the scales described above ($\alpha = 0.79/0.80$ for parents/adolescents).

Data processing methods

A descriptive analysis of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies, obtained using the developed and validated methodology, was conducted in SPSS. Mean values were calculated for all scales of the methodology for both parent and adolescent samples. The data were preliminarily controlled for potential influences of socio-demographic characteristics, including gender, age, parental education level, and family income. To analyze intergroup differences in the obtained mean values, Student’s t-test and Chi-square test were applied.

Results

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics on digital trust and readiness among parents and adolescents.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics on digital trust and readiness among parents and adolescents

	Parents		Adolescents		t
	N = 297 people		N = 297 people		
	M	SD	M	SD	
Reliability	4.08	0.71	5.15	0.66	5.49***
Safety	4.05	0.82	5.04	0.67	5.58***
Confidentiality	4.02	1.04	4.05	0.95	0.33
Digital literacy	3.89	1.15	5.02	0.96	9.78***
Digital Trust and Readiness	4.01	0.93	4.82	0.81	4.63***

Note: M – mean value; SD – standard deviation; *** p < 0.001.

As shown in Table 2, almost all indicators of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies exhibit significant differences between parents and adolescents.

In the parent sample, the highest mean scores were observed on the Reliability scale, which also had the smallest standard deviation, indicating a high degree of consensus in participants' assessments. The lowest mean score was observed on the Digital Literacy scale, which exhibited the largest standard deviation, suggesting considerable variability in participants' evaluations of this aspect of digital trust and readiness.

In the adolescent sample, the highest mean scores, as in the parent sample, were observed on the Reliability scale, along with the smallest standard deviation. The lowest mean score was observed on the Confidentiality scale, whereas both the Confidentiality and Digital Literacy scales showed the highest standard deviations, indicating greater variability in adolescents' assessments.

Regarding intergroup differences between parents and adolescents, the largest discrepancies were observed on the Digital Literacy scale, while no significant differences were found on the Confidentiality scale.

Next, we turn to intergroup comparisons across other socio-demographic characteristics. Table 3 presents data for parents and adolescents who demonstrated above-average levels of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies (>3.5).

As shown in Table 3, the largest proportion of individuals demonstrating high levels of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies are those with higher education, higher income, and a low level of religiosity, regardless of their region of residence. At the same time, a significant intergroup difference in religiosity was observed between parents and adolescents.

Next, we turn to a discussion of the results obtained.

Table 3. Descriptive analysis of the sample by main socio-demographic characteristics

	Parents (>3.5)	Adolescents (>3.5)	χ^2	p
Level of digital trust and readiness	N = 187 people (63.3%)	N = 224 people (75.42%)		
Socio-demographic characteristics				
Family income				
High (1.2)	118 (63.1%)			
Low (3.4)	69 (36.9%)			
Place of residence				
Yaroslavl oblast	84	110		
Moscow	103	114	0.37	0.86
Level of religiosity				
High	57 (30.5%)	42 (18.8%)		
Low	130 (69.5%)	182 (81.2%)	12.1	0.001
Level of education				
Higher	112 (59.9%)			
Secondary	47 (25.1%)			
General average	28 (15%)			

Discussion of results

According to our results, there are intergenerational differences in the level of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies. The greatest intergenerational differences were observed in the component of digital trust and readiness referred to as Digital Literacy, with adolescents demonstrating higher scores than their parents. This finding can be explained by the fact that, in general, adolescents tend to be more open to new experiences than the older generation, and are therefore more active in mastering new technologies.

In our previous study, we found that openness to new experiences is particularly significant for the younger generation (Dubrov 2019). In that study, adolescents exhibited the highest values specifically in the domain of openness to change, according to S. Schwartz's theory of values (Dubrov 2019). This indicates that it is important for young people to gain new experiences by exploring the world around them, which is rapidly evolving, including due to the active emergence of new technologies (Soldatova and Rasskazova 2020). Such openness facilitates faster socialization and adaptation to changing living conditions (Davis 2013; Douglas and McGarty 2001; Lee 2009). This explains why adolescents are more active in mastering digital technologies compared to their parents.

In addition, adolescents are not burdened with the responsibilities and obligations faced by parents in providing for the family. Consequently, they have more time available to devote to mastering digital technologies. According to cognitive load theory, the brain's ability to process and store new information in long-term memory declines with age (Paas et al. 2010), which may create a barrier to acquiring new digital skills. At the same time, the older generation's distrust of these technologies may reflect a defensive response to a perceived inability to master all modern digital tools.

Another explanation for this finding is that the current generation of adolescents, unlike the older generation, has grown up in the era of digital technologies. As a result, they are familiar with digital tools from early childhood, making it easier for them to learn and adopt new technologies. This familiarity contributes to their higher scores on the Digital Literacy scale.

However, this scale also shows the greatest standard deviation among adolescents, indicating considerable heterogeneity in respondents' assessments of the items. This can be explained by the fact that, despite the active development and implementation of digital technologies in daily life, not all segments of the population have equal access to them. Studies suggest that this phenomenon is related to digital inequality, which is often associated with low socio-economic status; families with limited income and education may be unable to afford modern devices that support these technologies (Abdulrazaq and Razlini 2020; Wessels 2013; Yu 2006). Consequently, children from such families have limited experience interacting with digital technologies and, accordingly, tend to score lower on this scale. This pattern is also reflected in our results, where families with higher levels of education and income demonstrate greater engagement with digital technologies compared to families with lower levels of education and income (Alesina et al. 2002; Putnam 2000).

At the same time, using the two regions studied as examples, we did not find any regional differences in the level of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies. This may be explained by the success of the country's large-scale digitalization initiatives, which aim to increase Internet accessibility across Russian regions, including rural areas, through libraries and cultural institutions.

In addition, there is evidence that some parents deliberately limit their adolescents' use of digital technologies, providing, for example, only basic models of mobile phones for quick

communication. According to these parents, such restrictions protect their children from the negative effects of digital technologies and potential digital addiction (Wei et al. 2011; Wessels 2013). This may explain the relatively low proportion of highly religious individuals who exhibit high levels of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies.

Regarding digital privacy, both parents and adolescents rated this aspect of digital trust and readiness at an average level. Moreover, no significant differences between the groups were observed for this indicator. This finding may be explained by the ongoing issue of personal data leakage, which can be exploited for criminal purposes. Frequent media reports on such incidents may reduce trust in digital technologies and the willingness to use them. In contrast, a study of digital trust in Sweden found that individuals place a high value on this component of digital trust and generally express confidence in the security of their personal data (Tunca and Anselmsson 2022).

In the same digital environment, the issue of the “digital footprint” is actively discussed. This concept refers to the leakage of personal data and its transfer to third parties without users’ knowledge or consent. Such incidents can contribute to the development of technophobia, a psychological phenomenon characterized by fear and reluctance to use new technologies in daily life (Soldatova et al. 2021). Consequently, individuals of all ages are concerned about this issue, which can pose a significant barrier to the adoption of digital technologies. This highlights the need for legislative mechanisms to combat cybercrime and ensure the secure storage of personal data, thereby increasing public trust in digital technologies.

Conclusions and limitations of the study

1. Significant differences between parents and adolescents are observed across nearly all indicators of digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies. Adolescents demonstrate higher digital trust and greater willingness to use digital technologies in their daily lives compared to their parents.
2. Among parents, the highest scores are observed on the digital trust and readiness component Reliability, while the lowest scores are observed on the Digital Literacy component.
3. Among adolescents, the highest scores are also observed on the Reliability component, similar to the parent sample, whereas the lowest scores are observed on the Confidentiality component.
4. The absence of significant differences between parents and adolescents on the Confidentiality component indicates that, despite the active integration of digital technologies into daily life, the problem of personal data leakage persists and requires systematic attention.

Future studies should incorporate qualitative methods, such as interviews or focus groups, and expand the number of respondents to allow for a comprehensive intergroup comparison across all socio-demographic parameters. The current sample size does not permit a full comparison of this kind, which is an objective for future research.

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References

- Abdulrazaq KA, Razlini MR (2020) Digital Literacy and the Performance E-Government: Evaluating the Moderating Role of Gender as a Demographic Factor. *Asia Proceedings of Social Sciences* 6(2): 112–116. <https://scispace.com/pdf/digital-literacy-and-the-performance-of-e-government-53twhz1v9s.pdf>
- Ajzen I (1985) From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior. In: Kuhl J, Beckmann J (Eds) *Action Control: From Cognition to Behavior*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 11–39. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-69746-3_2
- Alesina A, La Ferrara E (2002) Who trusts others? *Journal of Public Economics* 85(2): 207–234. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2727\(01\)00084-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2727(01)00084-6)
- Bandura A (1977) Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review* 84 (2): 191–215. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0033-295x.84.2.191>
- Calvani A, Fini A, Ranieri M (2009) Assessing digital competence in secondary education-Issues, models and instruments. *Issues in information and media literacy: Education, practice and pedagogy*: 153–172. <https://flore.unifi.it/handle/2158/328911>
- Campbell DT, Fiske DW (1959) Convergent and discriminant validation by the multitrait-multimethod matrix. *Psychological Bulletin* 56(2): 81–105. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0046016>
- Davis K (2013) Young people's digital lives: The impact of interpersonal relationships and digital media use on adolescents' sense of identity. *Computers in Human Behavior* 29(6): 2281–2293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.05.022>
- Digital Society Index 2019: Human Needs in a Digital World <https://www.oxfordeconomics.com/resource/digital-society-index-2019-human-needs-in-a-digital-world/>
- Douglas KM, McGarty C (2001) Identifiability and self-presentation: Computer-mediated communication and intergroup interaction. *British journal of social psychology* 40 (3): 399–416. <https://doi.org/10.1348/014466601164894>
- Dubrov DI (2019) Family social capital as a factor in intergenerational value transmission. PhD Thesis, Moscow, Russia: National Research University Higher School of Economics.
- Fedorova TL, Scheglova OA (2010) *Ehtimologicheskij slovar' russkogo yazyka: 60 tysyach slov* [Etymological dictionary of the Russian language: 60 thousand words]. LadKom, Moscow, 607 pp.
- Gallo LC, Smith TW, Cox CM (2006) Socioeconomic status, psychosocial processes, and perceived health: An interpersonal perspective. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine* 31(2): 109–119. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15324796abm3102_2
- Hunady J, Fendekova J, Orviska M (2020) Attitudes and trust to recent digital technologies: Using standards to improve them. In: 25th EURAS Annual Standardisation Conference–Standards for Digital Transformation: Blockchain and Innovation, Glasgow, Scotland, June, 10–12.
- Koch LV, Koch YuV (2019) Analysis of existing approaches to measurement of digital economy. *St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University Journal. Economics* 12 (4): 78–89. <https://doi.org/10.18721/JE.12407> (In Russian)
- Lee SJ (2009) Online communication and adolescent social ties: Who benefits more from Internet use? *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 14(3): 509–531. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2009.01451.x>
- Orlandi LB, Febo V, Perdichizzi S (2022) The role of religiosity in product and technology acceptance: Evidence from COVID-19 vaccines. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 185: 122032. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122032>

- Paas F, Tuovinen JE, Tabbers H, Van Gerven PW (2010) Cognitive load measurement as a means to advance cognitive load theory. *Educational Psychologist* 38(1): 63-71. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15326985EP3801_8
- Putnam RD (2000) *Bowling alone: The collapse and revival of American community*. Simon & Schuster.
- Soldatova GU, Nestik TA, Rasskazova EI, Dorokhov EA (2021) Psychodiagnostics of technophobia and technophilia: development and testing a questionnaire of attitudes towards technology for adolescents and parents. *Social Psychology and Society* 12 (4): 170–188. <https://doi.org/10.17759/sps.2021120410> (In Russian)
- Soldatova GU, Rasskazova EI (2020) Digital Transition Outcomes: From Online Reality to Mixed Reality. *Cultural-Historical psychology* 16 (4): 87-97. <https://doi.org/10.17759/chp.2020160409> (In Russian)
- Soomro MA, Hizam-Hanafiah M, Abdullah NL (2020) Digital Readiness Models: A Systematic Literature Review. *Compusoft: An International Journal of Advanced Computer Technology* 9 (3): 3596–3605.
- Strazzullo S (2024) Fostering digital trust in manufacturing companies: Exploring the impact of industry 4.0 technologies. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge* 9(4): 100621. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2024.100621>
- Tatarko AN, Maklasova EV, Lepshokova ZK, Galyapina VN, Efremova MV, Dubrov DI, Bultseva MA, Bushina EV, Mironova AA (2020) Assessment methodology of involvement in information and communication technology using. *Social Psychology and Society* 11 (1): 159-179. <https://doi.org/10.17759/sps.2020110110> (In Russian)
- Tunca B, Anselmsson J (2022) Lund Digital Trust Survey 2022. URL: https://portal.research.lu.se/files/117235497/Lund_Digital_Trust_2022.pdf
- US Digital Trust Study: Which social media platforms have the highest levels of digital trust among social users. <https://www.businessinsider.com/intelligence/digital-trust-enterprise-report-preview>.
- Veselov YuV (2020) Trust in a digital society. *Vestnik of Saint Petersburg University. Sociology* 13 (2): 129–143. <https://doi.org/10.21638/spbu12.2020.202> (In Russian)
- Vidiasova L, Kabanov Y (2020) Online trust and ICTs usage: findings from St. Petersburg, Russia. In: *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance*, 847-850.
- Wei KK, Teo HH, Chan HC, Tan BCY (2011) Conceptualizing and Testing a Social Cognitive Model of the Digital Divide. *Information Systems Research* 22(1): 170–187.
- Wessels B (2013) The reproduction and reconfiguration of inequality: Differentiation and class, status and power in the dynamics of digital divides. In: Ragnedda M, Muschert G (Eds) *The Digital Divide. The Internet and social inequality in international perspective*, 17-28.
- Yu L (2006) Understanding Information Inequality: Making Sense of the Literature of the Information and Digital Divides. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science* 38 (4): 229–252. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000606070600>
- Zhuravlev AL, Nestik TA (2018) Socio-psychological determination of the individual's readiness to use new technologies. *Psikhologicheskii zhurnal [Psychological journal]* 39 (5): 5–14. (In Russian)

Information about the author

- Dmitrii Igorevich Dubrov – PhD, Associate Professor, Senior Research Fellow, Center for Sociocultural Research, Psychology Department, Faculty of Social Science of HSE University. Moscow, 101000, Russia. E-mail: ddubrov@hse.ru

Appendix

Assessment of Structural Validity and Internal Consistency of the “Digital Trust and Digital Readiness” Questionnaire Scales

Figure A1. Assessment of the overall structure of digital trust and readiness (parents). *Note:* $\chi^2/df = 3.21$; CFI = 0.96; RMSEA = 0.04; SRMR = 0.05; PCLOSE = 0.35; *** $p < 0.001$

Figure A2. Assessment of the overall structure of digital trust and readiness (adolescents). *Note:* $\chi^2/df = 3.23$; CFI = 0.95; RMSEA = 0.05; SRMR = 0.06; PCLOSE = 0.33; *** $p < 0.001$

Table A1. Assessment of the internal consistency of the scales of the methodology for measuring digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies (parents)

Scale	Number of points	α
Reliability	5	0.76
Safety	4	0.84
Confidentiality	5	0.87
Digital literacy	6	0.77

Table A2. Assessment of the internal consistency of the scales of the methodology for measuring digital trust and readiness to use digital technologies (adolescents)

Scale	Number of points	α
Reliability	5	0.75
Safety	6	0.86
Confidentiality	4	0.89
Digital literacy	6	0.73

Assessment of the Convergent Validity of the "Digital Trust and Readiness to Use Digital Technologies" Questionnaire Scales

Figure A3. Relationship between digital trust and ICT readiness and use (parents). *Note:* $\chi^2/df = 1.88$; CFI = 0.95; RMSEA = 0.04; SRMR = 0.04; PCLOSE = 0.80; *** $p < 0.001$

Figure A4. Relationship between digital trust and ICT readiness and use (adolescents). *Note:* $\chi^2/df = 2.33$; CFI = 0.93; RMSEA = 0.05; SRMR = 0.05; PCLOSE = 0.50; *** $p < 0.001$

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Table A3. Correlation between digital trust and readiness indicators and attitudes towards technology

Sample	N	R
Adolescents	214	0.87**
Parents	143	0.78**

Note: ** $p < 0.01$.